

200 100 0 200 km

- ▲ archaeological site
- border
- city
- river
- Lake/Sea
- COUNTRY

DEM: Natural Earth 2 v3.2
 Admin: The World Bank
 Hydro: Natural Earth, OSM

Projection: WGS 1984
 Datum: WGS 1984

